
Mi Bicycle

Mitigation and adaption through better Biomass CYcling in Crop Livestock systems of north and western Europe

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Report on the current situation of case studies

Mette Vestergaard Odgaard, Lucas Soerensen, Wytse Vonk, Tom Schut, Renske Hijbeek, Guillaume Martin, Julie Ryschawy, Christine Watson, Kairsty Topp, Aude Pelletier and Tommy Dalgaard

General description

This report describes the case study regions in MiBicycle and elaborates on the future opportunities/scenarios to enhance better use of co-products for each region. Finally, system delineation is initiated.

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1. Introduction to the current situation of case studies

This deliverable (D1.1) describes the circularity in mixed crop and livestock farming systems in the four case studies. Increasing the circularity in mixed systems are potential solutions to climate change mitigation and adaptation (nutrient cycling, GHG emissions, carbon sequestration and productivity). Furthermore, data collection programmed in context of WPs 2-4 are briefly documented. The deliverable also describes other relevant local activities in the case studies. As the purpose of WP1 is to describe the sites, the modeling approach will be further elaborated in WP2.

More specifically, this report is based on the work done in task 1.2 – 1.5. At the first annual project meeting in Denmark (June 7-9, 2022, Figure 1-4), each partner was asked to produce a poster presenting their respective case study. This was based on a poster template produced by WP1 leaders.

This initiate by giving an overview of the four case studies based on the posters describing each region followed by a project system-delineation where the work packages are linked together.

2. Case studies

In the MiBicycle project, the case studies are located in The Netherlands, Denmark, Scotland, and France The template was comprised of 1) case study description with maps, graphs, figures representing the region, 2) fact summary boxes, and 3) system description and delineation.

a. The Netherlands - Drenthe (Task 1.2)

The Dutch case study region is Drenthe, which covers 268000 ha, figure 1. Agriculture has been important in the region for a long time. Agriculture covers 70% of the area with patches of nature remaining such as forest and heathland. The soils are mainly of a sandy texture, in patches covered by oligotrophic peatland. In some areas, all this peat has been excavated in the past for fuel, leaving a sandy soil behind with a large carbon content but a low soil fertility. Heathland was part of the plaggen culture where topsoil “plaggen” were extracted and used for bedding material of animals, mining the soils resulting in large areas with heath. With the introduction of synthetic fertilizer, most of the heathland was again made suitable for agriculture. Lowland more eutrophic peat soils were drained and are currently used for dairy with some grazing.

Currently the regulatory focus is on nitrogen deposition (mainly ammonia from intensive livestock farming systems dairy, pigs), but water quality (mainly caused by nitrate and phosphate pollution) is likely to become a problem for farmers in the near future. This could potentially result in future regulations limiting the use of fertilizers and/or manure, or the number of livestock that can be kept, and thus increasing the economic pressure on farmers. Biodiversity loss due to the extensive use of pesticides will be another challenge for the region.

The agricultural sector represents a mix of specialised dairy, pig, poultry and arable farms with some mixed farms. Many dairy farms allow their animals some grazing, although intensive farms without grazing are also present. Organic farms represent 3% of the total number of farms. The agricultural land is covered by 54% with grass and fodder crops, 1% horticulture and 45% other arable land. Some farms are highly specialized (e.g. starch potato and sugar beet processing industry). Pig and poultry farms heavily depend on concentrates, including a

large proportion of imported products. Also, dairy farms also rely on imported concentrates. Hence, the total feed imports into the region is considerable. The arable farms in the region are also specialized with rotations typically including starch potato, onion, sugar beet and wheat. Most of the crops are processed with the co-products used as feed.

Manure is mostly applied directly on land. Occasionally, a mono-digester is present on-farm. Also, multiple large co-digesting facilities are present within the region. At present, city sewage waste is not recycled. Farms are typically specialised and do not collaborate with other farms and farm types. Hence, there is some potential to increase circularity and better use local resources to reduce external inputs to the system.

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

MI BICYCLE case study region: Drenthe, The Netherlands

Wytse J. Vonk, A.G.T. Schut, Renske Hijbeek, Martin K. van Ittersum (2022)

Figure 1: Regional P flow diagram of Drenthe. Arrow thickness is indicative for the current situation. The mainly linear system is characterized by large inputs of feed and fertiliser from outside the region. The agricultural products, such as starch potato, milk, and meat are often directly exported from the region. On the other hand, products for consumption are mainly imported. A major part of P waste streams is not recycled.
 Agriculture is dependent on external imports and products are mostly exported out of the region (as illustrated in Figure 1). Better integration of crop (NE) and livestock farms (SW) could reduce feed imports. For example by cultivating feed for intensive livestock systems and returning manure (Figure 2). In the region, other options exist to reduce imports. For example by recycling city and food industry waste streams (Figure 1). Other co-products (Table 1) have potential to further increase the systems performance and circularity.

Figure 2: Regional P flows of agriculture in Drenthe. Arrow thickness is indicative for the current situation. The largest fraction of total import consists of feed. Limited amount of P is cycled back from the food system. Animal manure is used to fertilise crops, of which silage maize and grass are used to feed grazing animals (mainly dairy). Feed for intensive livestock is mostly imported from outside the region.

Table 1: List of co-products in the agro-food system in Drenthe, structured by the different components in the P flow diagrams (Figure 1&2).

Origin	Co-product	Usage	Co-product
Arable farm	Starch	Food industry	Wine & grain
	Cake residues from potato, sugar, beer, other crops		Wine
	Catchings from meat/abuses on the farm		Animal waste
	Green manure		Beet pulp
Livestock zone	Dairy slurry		Beetroot
	Dairy solid manure		Slaughterhouse waste
	Chicken manure		Residual sand, washed from roof/water cross
	Pig slurry		Waste water cleaning machines
	Soiled hay	Other	Vegetable, fruit and garden waste
	Catchings from meat/abuses on the farm		Wood chips
	Inspect meat/other waste		Wood chips
			Wink (batter) grouting in beer (20-25 liter)
			Sludge production (wastewater treatment)
			Crumb (from meatroom collection)

Figure 1: Poster representing the region of Drenthe in The Netherlands. The top of the poster illustrates the case study region in maps, the middle illustrates fact boxes, and the bottom gives examples of the system.

i. Other local activities and future scenarios – The Netherlands

Drenthe is also part of CAN-DO-IT (funded by NWO, the Dutch Science Foundation), and MIXED and SUREfarm projects (funded by EU Horizon 2020), providing strong leverage options.

The future opportunities/scenarios to climate change and adaption (nutrient cycling, GHG emissions, carbon sequestration and productivity) for this region include increased collaboration between crop and livestock farmers that may reduce dependency on external inputs. For example, more land could be exchanged giving the opportunity to widen crop rotations and grow more food locally. Another option is increasing the use of biogas production and application of digestate as fertilizer. Further, the farming system can benefit from a better (re)use of sewage system waste and other city waste streams, decreasing dependence on external fertilisers.

b. Denmark - Central region (Task 1.3)

In Denmark, the main land use is agriculture which covers 61%. Nature covers 25% in total and 13% is forest. Despite an overrepresentation of agriculture, the Danish landscape shows a significant geographical variation in other geophysical, hydrological and landscape elements such as nitrogen retention, coastal nitrogen loads, soil types, soil organic carbon, biodiversity, and farm type and practices. The case area is mainly dominated by sand and loamy soils.

The Danish case study is situated in Northern Jutland and represents part of the Limfjord catchment, which connects the North Sea and the Kattegat (Figure 2), and covers an area of 260000 ha where approximately 63% is agriculture. Furthermore, the Limfjord catchment is within the national range of both biodiversity scores (0-16 score – where 20 is the highest at national level) and N retention percentages (5-100%), and is therefore representative of Denmark. However, the Limfjord represents a catchment with some of the poorest ecological status and thus higher nitrogen reduction goals are required in this region relative to the rest of Denmark in order for the region to meet the goals of the European Water Framework Directive. The national coastal N reduction goal is approximately 13000 tons N/yr. by 2027. The target for the catchment surrounding the Limfjord is approximately 28% of the total, and half of this should be reduced from the chosen case study area (1500 tons N/yr.).

The agricultural diversity represents a mix of livestock and arable farms. The area has approximately 30% grass and 70% cropland and crop types are mainly grass and cereal grown in conventionally and intensive systems.

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Mitigation and adaptation through better Biomass Cycling in Crop-Livestock systems of north and western Europe

Case study description: Danish site

Authors: Mette V. Odgaard, Sara Iversen, Tommy Dalgaard

Case study description: Livestock and arable farm with biogas and biorefinery to balance feed, fodder and manure use and reduce emissions

The region in short: The Central Denmark Region represents the major and most specialized agriculture and livestock intensive western parts of Denmark, and have extensive data available for upscaling and generalization. The area has sandy-loamy moraines (about 40-70 m above sea level) and is dominated by agriculture with rotation cropping systems.

Impacts of alternative residue scenarios on GHG emissions/ C sequestration, productivity, and nutrient cycling is a focus area, including improved interactions between specialized arable and livestock production systems via exchange of manure, fodder and land use changes, to achieve ambitious GHG and N reduction targets. In particular the Limfjord estuary is regarded a critical case for eutrophication, and Denmark has a goal to reduce 13,000 ton N/yr. by the year 2700 where 28% of this should be reduced from the catchment surrounding the Limfjord. Therefore, the area provides high potential to mitigate effects from climate change, via the implementation of new technologies like biogas, biochar, biorefinery, adapted peatland soil management, etc. to support green growth and transition.

Facts as summary boxes

<p>Site description/landscape:</p> <p>Climate: Temperate climate</p> <p>Terrain - e.g. slope: Generally flat - 40-70m above sea-level. The highest point in Denmark is 171m above sea level.</p> <p>Soil type: Sandy soils, relatively unfertile compared to Eastern parts of Denmark.</p> <p>Land cover: Dominated by agriculture</p> <p>Total area of region: 140,000 ha</p>	<p>Farm characteristics:</p> <p>Total size: Medium sized - 70 ha</p> <p>Farm types: Cattle, plant and mixed</p> <p>Arable vs. grassland: The region has approx. 30% grass and 70% cropland. National: 20% - 80%</p> <p>Crop types: Grass and cereal</p> <p>Livestock type: Cattle</p> <p>Intensive: extensive, Conventional</p>	<p>Models of circularity:</p> <p>Model: The circular model - not fully functioning yet</p>	<p>Social data "status":</p> <p>Elaborate on existing potential conflicts and opportunities/collaboration from farmers' and other stakeholders' perspective.</p> <p>- Descriptive social demographic data</p>
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System description and delineation

WP 1, D1.1: Framework of the current situation is described and data mapping reported. A poster for each case study is produced for the first annual project meeting 7-9 June in Denmark.

Figure 2: Poster representing the region of Denmark. The top of the poster illustrates the case study region in maps, the middle illustrates fact boxes, and the bottom gives examples of the system

i. Other local activities and future scenarios – Denmark

The Danish case site is also part of the MIXED project (funded by EU Horizon 2020), which is focused on building a more robust collaboration between farms. Furthermore, the Trans4Num project will also work in the same area concentrating on implementing nature-based solutions to lower climatic footprint. Finally, a model to calculate circular systems is currently being developed in the project CIRCULAR (see appendix). If possible, this model will be tested for the Danish site and compared to result from the model output in WP2 in MiBicycle.

The future opportunities/scenarios to climate change and adaption (nutrient cycling, GHG emissions, carbon sequestration and productivity) for this region includes building a system that integrates livestock and arable farms with biogas and biorefinery to balance feed, fodder and manure with increased collaboration between farms - (Figure 6).

c. Scotland - Northeast region (Task 1.4)

The Scottish northeastern case study region is Fife (figure 3). The region represents a broad spectrum of land classes from highly productive land with productive clay soils, rich in organic matter, and relatively freely drained to poor grazing lands. However, the soils are coarse textured and stoney. The area covers 97.051 ha with grass covering 33 % and other arable land covering 54%. Moreover, the region represents some forest, golf courses, and urban areas.

The area represents all the farm enterprise of Scotland and is composed of beef and sheep, dairy, pigs, and poultry being mainly intensive and conventional. These farm types are often disconnected with little collaboration. Within this area, there is 24% of the Scottish barley area, 39% wheat, 62% potatoes and 63% of the vegetables for human consumption.

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Mitigation and adaptation through better Biomass Cycling in Crop Livestock systems of north and western Europe

Case study description: Scottish Case Study – Fife

Authors: Kairsty Topp, Christine Watson

Case study description

Facts as summary boxes

<p>Site description/landscape:</p> <p>Climate: Atlantic North Terrain – e.g. slope: Soil type: highly productive brown earths relatively freely drained and rich in organic matter Land cover - highly productive land towards the South and East suited to agricultural and horticultural production to poor rough grazing land. Other: Forestry, Golf courses, urban areas</p>	<p>Farm characteristics:</p> <p>Total size: 97051 Farm types: cropping & grass, mixed, keef & sheep Arable vs grassland: 52065:32461 ha Crop types: cereals, rape, potatoes, veg, orchard crops & fruit Livestock type: beef & sheep, dairy, pigs & poultry Intensive/extensive: mainly intensive Organic/conventional: mainly conventional</p>	<p>Models of circularity</p> <p>Model: within farm off-farm manure / straw anaerobic digester (waste veg products) brewers gas (feed to livestock)</p>	<p>Social data "status":</p> <p>Collaboration opportunities: farmer to farmer farmers and distillers farmers – anaerobic digestors</p>
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System description and delineation

Figure 3: Poster representing the region of Scotland. The top of the poster illustrates the case study region in maps, the middle illustrates fact boxes, and the bottom gives examples of the system

i. Other local activities and future scenarios – Scotland

The Scottish case site is also part of the MIXED project (funded by EU Horizon 2020), which is focused on building a more robust collaboration between farms..

The future opportunities/scenarios to climate change and adaption (nutrient cycling, GHG emissions, carbon sequestration and productivity) for this region is alternative utilization such as increased use of brewing products and increased collaboration between farms (Figure 6). There are also opportunities for sheep to graze cover crops and winter cereals, which will require collaboration between farms.

d. France - Ariège (Task 1.5)

The French case study is Ariège, Figure 4. This region (132000 ha agricultural land (27% of the total area)) differs from the others by having an oceanic Mediterranean climate. Moreover, the French landscape changes quickly over relatively small distances (valley, hilly, pre-mountain, mountain area) which has resulted in more specialized farms and low degree of circularity. The altitude ranges from <200m in the north to >700m in the south. The soil is clay and clay-limestone with relatively low organic matter (1.3-2.4%).

A large part of the north of the Ariège region, specialized in cash crop farms, is subject to several restrictions due to being considered a vulnerable area. These restrictions aim to reduce nitrate pollution of agricultural origin and to prevent new sources of pollution. These restrictions include spreading of fertilizer, manure storage, amount of nitrogen in manure.

The region holds approx. 2700 farms with an average size of 50ha. The main livestock type is cattle (26.5%) followed by sheep (18.5%) and dairy cattle (13%). There is 77% of grassland/fodder and 27% other crops. Grazing is low due to problems with bears and wolves. Generally, the crop rotation is restricted (maize-maize-maize or wheat-sunflower-wheat). The agriculture of each region can be seen in box 1-4 on figure 4.

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Mitigation and adaptation through better Biomass Cycling in Crop Livestock systems of north and western Europe

Case study description: French site - Ariège

Author : Julie Ryschawy

Case study description

Four soil & climate sub-regions...

- 1) Valley area (<200 m alt.)**
 - Specialized crop farms with monoculture of corn seeds and simple rotations (wheat-sunflower)/ few cover crops
 - Profitable cash crops yet production practices highly reliant on pesticides, mineral fertilizers and irrigation water
- 2) Hilly area (200 – 400 m alt.)**
 - Less-favorable conditions for cropping (shallow soils & slopes) → lower yields
 - More diversified cropping systems, including, oleaginous and protein crops, temporary and permanent grassland
- 3) Pre-mountain area (400 – 700 m alt.)**
 - Self-sufficient (crop-livestock systems (beef cattle, sheep)
 - Buying some soybean meals
 - Recycling their manure on-farm
- 4) Mountain area (>700 m alt.)**
 - Fully grassland-based area where cattle and sheep are raised with a low self-sufficiency in concentrates
 - Using mountain pastures during summer
 - Excess of manure with respect to the available land.

... leading to some divides...

- North-South** : different levels of accessibility from the cash crop valley to the mountainous livestock area
- Most economic and political activities located in the North
- East-West** : separated by main roads / two separated areas for public management

... and a lack of circularity

Long-term ongoing collaboration

- OG EIP Rotations 4/1000 since 2017
- Dynamix® co-design tool used with 3 farmer groups
- Co-design of by-product management scenarios at regional level
- New FAAB and MIXED project Focusing on local feed self-sufficiency

Facts as summary boxes

Site description/landscape:
 Climate : Oceanic with Mediterranean influence
 ~700 mm rain/year in the valley
 → 1 000 mm/year in the mountains
 Soil type : clay and clay-limestone soils
 → Organic matter : 1,3-2,4%
 → Slopes except in the valley area
 Land cover : only 27% land is UAA
 Main land-use : Woods (41%)

Farm characteristics :
 Total size : 132 000 ha UAA = 50 ha per farm in average
 2 700 farms (3 100 WCJ) → 15% decrease of farms 2000-2010
 Farm types :
 • 72% ruminant-oriented cattle (24,3% / sheep (8,8%)/Dairy cattle (13%)
 • 15,1% crop-livestock systems
 • 17,4% cash-crop oriented (inc. maize seeds)
 Arable vs grassland :
 27% crops / 77% grassland & fodder (inc. 27% of mountain pastures)

Models of circularity :
 Model : lacking at regional level → niche systems
 • Long-term 2-by-2 exchanges of straw/manure
 For local feed supply :
 • Hay and cereals bought locally by some livestock farmers to crop farmers
 • Covercrop grazing with some livestock farmers moving animals on few crop farms
 For local organic matter supply :
 • Pot. Supply = 76 000 t/y - Pot. Demand = 240 000 t/y
 • Few composting units and biogas units (manure/male seed/maize stalks)

Social data "status" :
 • Large push on organic farming
 22,7% of farms/13,9% of UAA
 • Direct sales highly developed :
 33% of farms doing short circuit sales/1% with on-farm processing
 • A regional natural park encouraging agritourism and local food democracy
 • Divided identity & lack of social capital between crop farmers and livestock farmers
 → Crop-livestock farmers as potential leaders

System description and delineation

Interaction of a mixed farming operation

WP1_D1.1 : Framework of the current situation is described and data mapping reported. A poster for each case study is produced for the first annual project meeting 7-9 June in Denmark
 Information from 2017, diagram made by Claire Triolet, INRAE, April 2022

Figure 4: Poster representing the region of Ariège in France. The top of the poster illustrates the case study region in maps, the middle illustrates fact boxes, and the bottom gives examples of the system

i. Other local activities and future scenarios – France

The French case site is also part of the MIXED project (funded by EU Horizon 2020), which is focused on building a more robust collaboration between farms.. The area is also the case study region for the FAAB project. The focus of this project is to develop local feed chain using cereals and proteins produced by the department's crop farmers to fatten Ariège animals.

The future opportunities/scenarios to climate change and adaption (nutrient cycling, GHG emissions, carbon sequestration and productivity) for this region is to increase biogas production, composting and grazing, cover crop grazing and collaboration between farmers (Figure 6). Currently there is little use of the biogas plant. Farmers already use much of their manure on the farm, but in the south, there is a large potential to increase circularity by moving manure from south to north. Some of the farmers wish to be more local (local fodder + sell local and be more self-sufficient).

3. System delineation initiation based on the case study descriptions

The system delineation and boundaries are defined (Figure 6) based on the case study descriptions. The system presented here is the first draft in the project and will be adjusted during the lifetime of the project period.

The delineation is designed to fit the current project composed of 4(5) work packages. WP1 provides the system delineation. In WP2 the focuses on the system components that are encompassed by the punctured line for which indicators on productivity, nutrient cycling, soil organic matter and greenhouse gas emissions, as a result of better use of co-products, will be assessed. WP3 and 4 embrace the entire system where WP3 defines the circular use of co-products - both inside and outside the system - and WP4 focus on the social aspect by including interests of both farmers inside the system and other interests outside the system. The methodology behind WP2 focusses on farms, hence it does not include off-farm processing and associated technologies as part of the calculations. Therefore, these are placed outside the system in figure 6. Other models such as the Circular model, described in the appendix do account for processing technologies as components inside the system and therefore, the system delineation would change if this model were to be used. Moreover, scale could also affect the delineation.

More specifically, the core of the system is animal, arable, and mixed farms (Figure 6). Each case study region will have at least two 'typical' or 'representative' farms. These do not need to be existing farms but can be a model farm which is representative for a farm type in the region. Processing for feed and soil amendments are usually done on-farm and hence considered as a component of the system, whereas processing for food, energy and raw materials with e.g. biorefinery and biogas is outside the system boundary. Arguments are as follows: if energy use and emissions or emission reductions should be attributed to another sector (i.e., food) only in-flows and out-flows and changes therein are relevant for a scenario study. When attributions are mainly to the agricultural system it should be inside the system boundary. The actions towards a better use of co-products are in the delineation described as "future opportunities" (Figure 6). Four are listed: 1) Increased collaboration, 2) new technologies, 3) composting - alternative utilization of N, P, CO₂ - divided into composting of crop residues, vegetable waste, manure or city waste products, and 4) biogas production (more manure) where (1) is common for all sites. Despite the similar future opportunity the agricultural change on the field resulting from increased collaboration (1) differs across countries by causing increased cover-crop grazing for Scotland and France, exchange of land resulting in more potato cultivations for the Netherlands, and more grass and grass in rotation for Denmark (Figure 6). Furthermore, composting is common for Netherlands, France and Scotland where composting is outside the system for the Netherlands, and both inside and outside for Scotland (Figure 6).

Inside or outside processing is illustrated by the punctured line which is not a fixed boundary but a boundary that can fluctuate to for example include processing for food, energy and raw materials. This means that the system delineation can change depending on the research question and scale.

For Denmark, one example of a flow from internal outputs to externalities is grass biomass from the farm which is used in the biorefinery (e.g. the red arrow in Figure 6). This becomes an external input to the farm (e.g., the blue arrow in figure 6) when the residue from the biorefinery is delivered back to the farm. In the Netherlands crop residues from the field can be transferred to a compost facility outside of the farm. This is an output from the system/internal outputs (e.g., the red arrow in figure 6). The processed residues from the

composting process that are applied on farm are then external inputs to the system (e.g., the blue arrow in figure 6).

As mentioned above, WP2 mainly focuses on physical identities of the system. That is, crop types and per species the number of animals. Hence, the future opportunities are identified in Figure 6 by underlined text. For example, a future opportunity to increase collaboration will result in increased cover-crop grazing and thereby an increase in the proportion of animal manure excreted in the field. Another example is the biorefinery: the biorefinery processing grass is the facilitator of a change providing the future opportunity, but the actual change is more grass in the rotation. Therefore, the current system delineation should be linked to method and the calculations of the indicators in WP2 (currently: Energy, Crop yield, and N₂O emissions).

We will aim for a common set of future opportunities, which will be assessed in each case study in WP2. In addition, each case study can also assess an alternative utilization option which is case study specific.

Effect on externalities such as land use, energy use, and GHG emissions can be made visible, either via impact on indicators or via quantification of opportunity costs when evaluating alternative circularity designs. Moreover, exogenous factors on the system such as subsidies and other legislation effects may drive decisions on how to use the land and thereby also the system delineation. Nevertheless, elaborations on these exogenous factors are not within the scope of this project.

Figure 6: Conceptual system delineation of the four regions. The flower encloses all elements handled in the project and illustrates items within and outside the system borders. This figure is a living framework and will change throughout the project period. See more in D1.2.

The author(s)/editor(s) acknowledge the financial support through the partners of the Joint Call of the Cofund ERA-Nets SusCrop (Grant N° 771134), FACCE ERA-GAS (Grant N° 696356), ICT-AGRI-FOOD (Grant N° 862665) and SusAn (Grant N° 696231).

4. Data collection and data mapping in context of WPs 2-4

Data collection will be initiated by WP2. The team from the Netherlands will hold individually meetings with each partner to clarify possible local data potential and to highlight differences between the regions. The indicators to be calculated are: crop production, nitrogen balance and cycling (incl. all its components), emissions of N₂O, CO₂, and CH₄, energy consumption and production and soil organic matter indicators. A more detailed method has been laid out in D2.1. See also D1.3 for the data management plan.

Appendix: Modelling circular systems – Denmark as case

As an example on how to analyze circularity in agro-ecological systems the model we use the model being built in a Danish research project – The CIRCULAR model.

The CIRCULAR model is being developed as the main output of the broader CIRKULÆR project (*Det cirkulære jordbrug: Systemanalyse af grøn biomasse til fødevarer, foder og energy* in Danish – *The circular land use: System analyses of green biomass for feed, fodder, and energy* in English) financed by Ministry of Food and Agriculture. The aim of the project is to conduct a holistic analysis of innovative biomass systems based on green biomass. This model will inspire WP2 on how to construct the analysis flow and the control of inputs and outputs. The CIRCULAR model is further developed in the MiBicycle project and tested in the Danish case study site. The model developed in WP2 in this project will be conducted in all sites.

a. The CIRCULAR model

Model design

The model is static and quantifies biomass flows in agriculture for a representative year in terms of required external input, turnover, products and losses (Appendix - figure 1).

The author(s)/editor(s) acknowledge the financial support through the partners of the Joint Call of the Cofund ERA-Nets SusCrop (Grant N° 771134), FACCE ERA-GAS (Grant N° 696356), ICT-AGRI-FOOD (Grant N° 862665) and SusAn (Grant N° 696231).

Appendix - figure 1: Illustration of the CIRCULAR model. In this model all “technologies” are part of the system. This includes e.g. biorefineries and biogas plants where biomass from the farm is processed. The coloured arrows circulating the model illustrate the flows of all input and outputs.

It is built up by a sequence of technologies (Appendix - figure 1), where the basic level and starting point is an area with a defined cultivation of a crop, for example barley on a sandy soil (headline “Field”). The subsequent steps represent various treatments and technologies applied to the produced crops and biomass (Step 1-3 technologies, Livestock). Often the technologies follow each other in a sequence; for example, the output from barley could go through the following three technologies: feed mill producing grain, fed to pigs and cattle and the resulting manure can be sent to a biogas plant.

Besides the products produced in the initial crop production level, there is import of external inputs, both into crop production (e.g. fertilizer and diesel) and into the different technologies (e.g. soy protein to a pig production site).

The technologies produce a range of products, which are either further treated in the model by other technologies, leaving the system as a true product, e.g. pork meat, or the products can subsidize some of the external input, like fertilizer for manure and thereby alternate these flow streams (although the model must stay static).

Based on the defined area of each crop and size of the different technologies (for example, number of dairy cows or amount of slurry treated at the biogas plant), the model calculates the external resources required at the different steps as well as the produced products (food, energy). Furthermore, the model quantifies the associated greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and other losses to the environment at each stage of the production cycle – based on mass balances of carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P).

Model engine and user interface

Excel is used as a user interface for inputting data while most model calculations and data management are done using the R scripting language.

Excel sheets named as *index cards* are used for inputting definitions of technologies (input and output functions/quantities), while excel *scenario files* are used for defining model scenarios (amounts of crops grown, technologies in production).

Current development status

As of May 2022, the 3 first steps in the model (Field crops, some step 1 technologies including dairy cattle) are working and nearly complete in terms of functionality. Additional technologies in step 2 and 3, as well as additional types of livestock to account for the current state of the agricultural system in Denmark will be added in the next version.

The aim is to test the model on the current state of agriculture and subsequently model alternative scenarios of the agricultural system. The model will also be set-up for different regions and/or larger catchment in comparison to the national level, based on geographically differentiated productivity and impacts. Hence, the model should be tested in the current case study site near the Limfjord in the Danish region in the current MiBicycle project.

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b. Relation to other case studies

The above description of the Circular Danish model serves as inspiration for the more general model built in WP2. The model from WP2 will be tested in all regions whereas the Circular model from Denmark will only be tested in Denmark. Furthermore, WP2 will produce guidelines on which data is required to calculate indicators for all project partners to streamline data collection.

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